

Kinetic study of redox reaction between diphenylbenzidine and thiosulfate

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The kinetics of the redox reaction between diphenylbenzidine (DPB) and thiosulfate was investigated in the range pH 2.0 to 4.5. Order of reaction with respect to thiosulfate, diphenylbenzidine and H^+ was found to be one.

The following rate law is recommended :

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{DPB}] [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] + k_2 K \{\text{DPB} [\text{H}^+]\} [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]$$

where k_1, k_2 are the rate constants for the reaction

having the values of $k_1 = 5.557 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 5.827 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

K is the protonation constant of DPB having value of $476 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Amines are widely distributed in nature. Their importance in industry as raw material, intermediates, finished products and in the laboratories is well documented. The amino group is endowed with a set of physical and chemical properties, which mainly depend on the presence of certain structural elements. On the basis of their structure, amines are classified as primary, secondary and tertiary amines. Diphenylbenzidine is an example of secondary amine and it is an oxidized product of diphenylamine¹. Thomas studied the oxidation of radical products formed following the oxidation of diphenylamine. He reported the detection of a relatively stable radical derived from phenyl- α -naphthylamine when this compound was used to inhibit auto-oxidation of 1-octadecane at 170°C ². Yamashita *et al.* studied the base equilibrium of secondary amines on the surface of sodium dodecyl sulphate micelle by means of the ultrasonic absorption method³. Hoskins also studied the reaction of diphenylamine with different oxidants⁴. Prasad and Srivastava studied on an amino derivative of vanadium tetrachloride with secondary and tertiary amines⁵. Kinetic study involving diphenylbenzidine has not been reported so far, though studies on electron transfer phenomenon continues to appear in the literature⁶⁻¹⁰. In this work the kinetic study of the reaction between diphenylbenzidine and sodium thiosulfate is reported. The stability of diphenylbenzidine and the effect of H^+ concentration on rate of reaction have also been studied.

Results and discussion

The redox reaction was carried out under the pseudo first-order conditions having diphenylbenzidine > sodium thiosulfate. Kinetic data was collected using integration method by plotting $\ln A_\infty - A_t/A_\infty - A_0 - A_t$ vs time, where A_∞ stands for absorbance at infinite time, A_0 and A_t represent initial absorbance and absorbance at time t (s) as shown in Table 1. The plots obtained for constant concentration of sodium thiosulfate and varying concentration of diphenylbenzidine in all four ratios (1 : 10, 1 : 15, 1 : 20 and 1 : 25) produced a straight line passing through the origin. These plots indicate that the reaction is first order in sodium thiosulfate.

The stoichiometry of the reaction between diphenylbenzidine and thiosulfate is

Table 1. Values of k_{obs} at various concentration of diphenylbenzidine
 $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}] = 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 570 \text{ nm}$, $\epsilon = 4920 \text{ dm}^3/\text{mol cm}$,
 $T = 32^\circ$

Sl. no.	pH	5×10^{-5}	7.5×10^{-5}	10×10^{-5}	12.5×10^{-5}
1.	2.0	0.386	0.476	0.550	0.726
2.	2.5	0.190	0.370	0.480	0.600
3.	3.0	0.220	0.270	0.360	0.490
4.	4.0	0.245	0.315	0.374	0.426
5.	4.5	0.220	0.290	0.360	0.420

Effect of diphenylbenzidine on rate :

The plot of $\ln A_\infty - A_0/A_\infty - A_t$ vs time, for different pH values, helped to compute k_{obs} for each set of experiment. When these values of k_{obs} , for different sets, were plotted as a function of concentration of diphenylbenzidine, a straight line was obtained passing through the origin as shown in Fig. 1. From the slope of this line, the value of rate constant for second order was calculated.

Fig. 1. Determination of values of rate for second order of reaction by plotting k_{obs} vs [diphenylbenzidine] for pH 2.0–4.5, $[S_2O_3^{2-}] = 1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$: (◆) pH 2.0, (■) 2.5, (▲) 3.0, (×) 4.0, (*) 4.5.

Effect of $[H^+]$ on rate of reaction :

To study the effect of $[H^+]$ on rate of reaction, kinetic runs were carried out at different pH values under similar experimental conditions. It was observed that rate increases with the increase in hydrogen ion concentration. The plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ produced a straight line with positive slope (Table 2, Fig. 2).

pH	2.0	2.5	3.0	4.0	4.5
$[H^+], M$	0.010	0.0032	0.0010	0.0001	0.000032
$k', \text{ dm}^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	8927.2	7126.2	5714.3	5626.4	5391.9

Fig. 2. Plot of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ for the determination of effect of hydrogen ion concentration.

Proposed mechanism :

The mechanism is suggested to incorporate the following three steps

The rate of the reaction according to the step 2 and 3 will be

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}] [S_2O_3^{2-}] + k_2 [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}H^+] [S_2O_3^{2-}] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Rate} = \{k_1 [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}] + k_2 [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}H^+]\} [S_2O_3^{2-}] \quad (5)$$

Assuming that the formation of the protonated specie $[C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}H^+]$ is quick, equilibrium constant K for the formation of protonated specie is represented as

$$K = \frac{[C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}H^+]}{[C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}][H^+]} \quad (6)$$

And therefore

$$K [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}][H^+] = [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}H^+] \quad (7)$$

Substituting $[C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}H^+]$ in eq. (5)

$$\text{Rate} = \{k_1 [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}] + k_2 K [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}][H^+]\} [S_2O_3^{2-}] \quad (8)$$

$$k_{obs} = k_1 [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}] + k_2 K [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}][H^+] \quad (9)$$

$$k_{obs} = [C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}] \{k_1 + k_2 K [H^+]\} \quad (10)$$

$$k' = k_1 + k_2 K [H^+] \quad (11)$$

For the indirect determination of order reaction for the diphenylbenzidine k' was obtained by plotting a graph between k_{obs} vs $[C_{12}H_{10}N_2C_{12}H_{10}]$. To determine the effect of $[H^+]$ concentration the values of k' were plotted against $[H^+]$ and the values of k_1 and k_2 were calculated from the slope and intercept and were found to be $k_1 = 5.557 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $k_2 = 5.827 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ respectively.

Experimental

All chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Kinetic measurement was carried out on Shimadzu UV-160, UV/Visible spectrophotometer using quartz cells. pH measurements were carried out on digital pH meter using a combined glass

Ag/AgCl electrode HI-1332.

Preparation of diphenylamine solution :

The stock solution of the diphenylamine was prepared at a concentration of 0.1 mol dm^{-3} by dissolving an appropriate amount in 99% methanol. The pH was maintained to a required value with the help of sodium acetate buffer. pH meter was used to validate the pH value.

Cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate :

The 0.1 M cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate stock solution was prepared in $0.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$. The pH of cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate was maintained to a required value with the help of sodium acetate buffer on HANNA 'HI-8314' pH meter.

Violet solution of diphenylbenzidine :

Diphenylbenzidine was prepared by mixing diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate solution in a ratio of 1 : 2. As a result of oxidation, violet solution of diphenylbenzidine was obtained.

Investigation of molar ratio between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate :

Molar ratio between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate was established through spectral analysis. For this purpose reaction mixture was maintained in a 3 cm^3 cuvet. The concentration of diphenylamine was kept constant ($2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and the concentration of cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate (1×10^{-4} , 2×10^{-4} and $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was varied in a ratio of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3, and that 1 : 2 ratio was found to be appropriate.

Determination of molar absorption coefficient :

Molar absorptivity of diphenylbenzidine was determined at 570 nm by recording absorbance of solutions having concentrations of 2×10^{-4} , 3×10^{-4} , 4×10^{-4} and $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively. It was found to be $4920 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Determination of the stability of diphenylbenzidine :

The reaction between diphenylamine and cerium(IV) sulfate tetrahydrate with a ratio of 1 : 2 was followed spectrophotometrically at 570 nm corresponding to absorbance maxima of diphenylbenzidine. The stability of diphenyl-

benzidine was studied at room temperature by varying the pH between 2.0–4.5. The absorbance values were recorded at an interval of 1 min. Reaction mixture of diphenylbenzidine is stable for 45 min after its formation at pH 4.0.

Kinetic measurements :

The kinetic study of the reduction of diphenylbenzidine by sodium thiosulfate was carried out under the pseudo first-order condition having $[\text{diphenylbenzidine}] > [\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}]$. Different combinations of both diphenylbenzidine and reductant (sodium thiosulfate) were prepared by taking constant concentration of the reductant ($1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and varying the concentrations of diphenylbenzidine (2×10^{-4} , 3×10^{-4} , 4×10^{-4} and $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). Acetic acid-sodium acetate buffer was used to maintain the pH range between 2.0–4.5. Various ratios of diphenylbenzidine and sodium thiosulfate solutions were mixed in a 1 cm quartz cell to a total volume of 3 cm^3 . Absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically as a function of time for each set of reaction mixture at 570 nm.

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